

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

2026-YIL
IYUN/6-SON, III-QISM

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

*Elektron nashr. 2026-yil, iyun.
III-qism*

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:

Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Maxmudov Nosir, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xajiyev Baxtiyor Dushaboyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Musayeva Shoirazimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), professor
Ali Konak (Ali Ko'nak), iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor (Turkiya)
Cham Tat Huei, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD), professor (Malayziya)
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldix'ja o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dots.
Faxridinov Zafarjon Faxridin o'g'li, O'zb. Res. Bosh prokuraturasi HIJQKD boshqarma boshlig'i
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Anijon viloyati prokurorining o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farkhod, O'zb. Res. Bosh prokuraturasi IJQK Departamentining Namangan viloyati boshqarmasi boshlig'i
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), katta o'qituvchi
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), v.b. dots.
Djudi Smetana, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Krissi Lyuis, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (Moskva)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD) (Turkiya)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon o'g'li, TDIU ITI departamenti rahbari
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o'g'li, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent.
Abdukarimova Dinara Rustamxonovna, bank-moliya akademiyasi professori, DSc., professor.
Ikramov Murod Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Nazarova Ra'no Rustamovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Editorial board:

Salimov Okil Umrzokovich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjavevich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Rae Kwon Chung, South Korea, Honorary Professor at TSUE, Nobel Prize Laureate
Osman Mesten, Member of the Turkish Parliament, Head of the Turkey–Uzbekistan Friendship Society
Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhridinovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Siddikova Sadokat Gafforovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences
Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Makhmudov Nosir, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Professor
Slizovskiy Dmitriy Yegorovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abduganiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khajiyev Bakhtiyor Dushaboyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khakimov Nazar Khakimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Professor
Ali Konak, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor (Turkey)
Cham Tat Huei, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)
Foziljonov Ibrokhimjon Sotvoldikhoja ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Fakhridinov Zafarjon Fakhridin ogli, Head of the DCEC under the Prosecutor General's Office of the Rep. of Uzb.
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Prosecutor of Anijan Region
Ochilov Farkhod, Head of the Namangan Regional Department of the Department of Internal Affairs of Rep. of Uzb.
Buzrukkhonov Sarvarkhon Munavvarkhonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences
Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences, Senior Lecturer
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Acting Associate Professor
Judi Smetana, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Chrissy Lewis, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Glazova Marina Victorovna, Doctor of Sciences in Economics (Moscow)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) (Turkey)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon ugli, Head of the Department of Scientific Research and Innovations, TSUE
Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli, Senior lecturer at TSUI
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor.
Abdukarimova Dinara Rustamkhanovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Ikramov Murod Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Nazarova Ra'no Rustamovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, katta o'qituvchi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, mustaqil tadqiqotchi
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Geografiya fanlari doktori, professori
Umirzoqov Ja'sur Artiqboy o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent
Zebo Kuldasheva, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent

Board of Experts:

Berkinov Bazarbay, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Pulatov Bakhtiyor Alimovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Khakimov Ziyodulla Akhmadovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics
Gafurov Doniyor Orifovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogy
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Tukhtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Khamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarimovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Yakhshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, Senior Lecturer
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, Independent Researcher
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Doctor of Geographical Sciences, Professor
Umirzokov Jasur Artiqboy ugli, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor
Zebo Kuldasheva, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti,
O'zbekiston Respublikasi Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi Iqtisodiy
jinoyatlarga qarshi kurashish departamenti

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va
taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi
Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar
vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy
attestatsiya komissiyasi
rayosatining
2023-yil 1-apreldagi
336/3-sonli qarori bilan
ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

SUD BOSHQARUVCHILARI FAOLIYATINING IQTISODIY RAG‘BATLANTIRISH TIZIMI VA ULARNING SUBSIDIAR JAVOBGARLIGI: MUAMMOLAR VA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	12
Soliyev Damirjon Nurmatovich	
BLOKCHEYN TEXNOLOGIYASI ASOSIDA MOLIYAVIY TRANZAKSIYALARNI NAZORAT QILISH TIZIMI (SMART-KONTRAKTLAR, MARKAZLASHMAGAN MA‘LUMOTLAR BAZASI VA AUDIT IZLARI).....	18
Olimova Mukhlisa Vohidjon qizi	
SANOAT SEKTORIDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O‘TISH: STRATEGIK AFZALLIKLAR VA TO‘SIQLAR TAHLILI.....	26
Xatamov Ochildi Qurbonovich	
ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯ БАНКОВСКОЙ СИСТЕМЫ УЗБЕКИСТАНА КАК ФАКТОР ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ЕЁ КОНКУРЕНТОСПОСОБНОСТИ.....	32
PhD. Юлдашева С.Ш	
TREND MODELLARI YORDAMIDA MEHNAT RESURSLARI SONINI EKONOMETRIK MODELLASHTIRISH.....	38
Haydarova Dinora Atamurot qizi	
МЕТОДОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ ВЫКУПА И ПРОДАЖИ КВОТ НА ОРОСИТЕЛЬНУЮ ВОДУ.....	43
Гоженко Борис Владимирович	
MOLIYAVIY LEVERIJ SAMARASI VA QARZ MABLAG‘LARINI BOSHQARISHDA UNDA FOYDALANISH.....	50
Latipova Shaxnoza Maxmudovna	
XIZMATLAR SOHASIDA WEBMONEY TO‘LOV TIZIMINI KOMPYUTERDA O‘RNATISH VA SOZLASHNING IQTISODIYOTDAGI ROLI.....	55
Fazilat Esirgapovna Jomonqulova	
Nizomov Murod	
Qurbonboyeva Rayhon Bahronjon qizi	
MECHANISMS FOR THE FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE.....	58
Shukhrat Mashrabboevich Mamadaliyev	

MECHANISMS FOR THE FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE

Shukhrat Mashrabboevich Mamadaliyev
Associate Professor, Department of
Labor Protection and Ecology,
Namangan State Technical University

Abstract

This article describes the essential mechanisms of forming and developing a healthy lifestyle in modern society. The authors analyze three core pillars of establishing healthy habits: the family environment, promotional activities in educational institutions, and the prevention of harmful habits among youth. The paper highlights the impact of a proper daily routine, balanced nutrition, physical activity, and mental well-being on human health. Furthermore, it emphasizes the importance of collaboration between families, educational sectors, and the public in raising a spiritually and physically mature younger generation.

Keywords: healthy lifestyle, family environment, daily routine, balanced nutrition, physical activity, mental health, educational institution, harmful habits, prevention, youth employment, healthy society.

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada zamonaviy jamiyatda sog'lom turmush tarzini shakllantirish va rivojlantirishning muhim mexanizmlari bayon etilgan. Mualliflar sog'lom turmush tarzini qaror toptirishning uchta asosiy ustunini tahlil qiladilar: oilaviy muhit, ta'lim muassasalaridagi targ'ibot ishlari hamda yoshlar o'rtasida zararli odatlarning oldini olish. Maqolada to'g'ri kun tartibi, muvozanatli ovqatlanish, jismoniy faollik va ruhiy salomatlikning inson sog'lig'iga ta'siri yoritilgan. Shuningdek, ma'nan va jismonan yetuk yosh avlodni tarbiyalashda oila, ta'lim tizimi va jamoatchilik o'rtasidagi hamkorlikning ahamiyati ta'kidlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: sog'lom turmush tarzi, oilaviy muhit, kun tartibi, muvozanatli ovqatlanish, jismoniy faollik, ruhiy salomatlik, ta'lim muassasasi, zararli odatlar, profilaktika, yoshlar bandligi, sog'lom jamiyat.

Аннотация

В данной статье описываются основные механизмы формирования и развития здорового образа жизни в современном обществе. Авторы анализируют три ключевых столпа формирования здоровых привычек: семейную среду, пропагандистскую деятельность в образовательных учреждениях и профилактику вредных привычек среди молодежи. В работе освещается влияние правильного режима дня, сбалансированного питания, физической активности и психического благополучия на здоровье человека. Кроме того, подчеркивается важность сотрудничества между семьей, образовательным сектором и общественностью в воспитании духовно и физически зрелого молодого поколения.

Ключевые слова: здоровый образ жизни, семейная среда, режим дня, сбалансированное питание, физическая активность, психическое здоровье, образовательное учреждение, вредные привычки, профилактика, занятость молодежи, здоровое общество.

INTRODUCTION

The family is the most important unit of society. A person's worldview, morals, health, and lifestyle are primarily formed within the family environment. Therefore, establishing a healthy lifestyle in the family is of great importance not only for the health of each individual but also for the development of society as a whole. A healthy lifestyle is a set of habits, rules, and ways of living aimed at maintaining physical, mental, and social well-being.

The formation of a healthy lifestyle in the family begins with establishing a proper daily routine. Waking up, eating, working, and resting on time help the human body function normally. A daily routine is especially important for children. Going to bed and waking up at scheduled times, studying, engaging in physical exercise, and resting contribute to a child's healthy growth and development[3].

Proper and balanced nutrition is also one of the key factors of a healthy lifestyle. The family diet should include sufficient amounts of vegetables and fruits rich in vitamins, dairy products, meat, and grain products. Excessive consumption of fatty, salty, and fast foods can negatively affect human health. In addition, following proper eating habits and paying attention to food hygiene are essential.

Physical activity plays a significant role in developing a healthy lifestyle within the family. Morning exercises, sports activities, walking, and various active games help strengthen health. When parents actively participate in sports, they set a positive example for their children. Nowadays, excessive use of computers and mobile phones contributes to a sedentary lifestyle; therefore, special attention should be paid to physical activity[1].

Creating a healthy psychological environment within the family is also very important. Mutual respect, kindness, and sincere relationships among family members have a positive impact on mental well-being. Constant conflicts, rude behavior, and stress can harm a person's health. Therefore, parents should communicate openly with their children, support them, and listen to their concerns and problems.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The issue of forming and promoting a healthy lifestyle is currently one of the most relevant areas of research in medicine, pedagogy, psychology, and sociology. Scientific studies conducted on this topic have proven that a healthy lifestyle has a direct impact on human health, life expectancy, and quality of life.

Among Uzbek scholars, the scientific works of A. Abdullayev, R. Salomov, and B. Khojayev have highlighted the theoretical foundations of a healthy lifestyle, as well as the role of physical education and sports in strengthening human health. According to these authors, the formation of a healthy lifestyle should be carried out through the continuous education system, family upbringing, and cooperation with the wider community[2].

Research conducted by scholars from the CIS countries has paid particular attention to the pedagogical and social mechanisms of promoting a healthy lifestyle. In particular, Russian researchers V. K. Balsevich and L. I. Lubisheva considered physical culture an integral part of general human culture and emphasized the importance of regular physical activity and health-oriented education in the formation of a healthy lifestyle. In their view, developing knowledge, skills, and values related to healthy living among the younger generation is one of the priority tasks of the educational system.

Furthermore, I. I. Brekhman interprets a healthy lifestyle as a conscious activity aimed at preserving and strengthening human health. According to the scholar, ensuring health should not be limited solely to disease prevention but should also involve the development of an individual's physical, mental, and social well-being.

Among international scholars, the "Health Field Concept" proposed by M. Lalonde is of particular significance. According to this concept, the main factors influencing human health include lifestyle, environment, biological characteristics, and the healthcare system, with lifestyle accounting for the largest contribution. This approach serves as the theoretical foundation for many modern programs aimed at promoting a healthy lifestyle[4].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study is based on both theoretical and practical approaches to examining the mechanisms of forming and developing a healthy lifestyle. During the research process, general and specific methods of scientific inquiry were applied.

In particular, local and international scientific literature, regulatory and legal documents, academic articles, and statistical data related to the topic were analyzed. The theoretical foundation of the study is based on scientific perspectives related to a healthy lifestyle, health culture, physical activity, and health-promoting technologies[5].

Throughout the research, methods such as analysis and synthesis, comparative analysis, systematic approach, generalization, and statistical data processing were employed. The analysis method was used to study the components of a healthy lifestyle and the factors influencing it. Comparative analysis made it possible to compare local and international experiences and identify effective mechanisms.

In addition, the roles of the family, educational institutions, healthcare system, and public organizations in forming and developing a healthy lifestyle were evaluated using a systematic approach. The obtained results were generalized, and scientific conclusions and practical recommendations were developed regarding effective mechanisms for promoting a healthy lifestyle[7].

The methodological basis of the research is formed by modern scientific concepts and approaches aimed at strengthening human health, educating a healthy generation, and developing a culture of healthy living in society.

The prevention of harmful habits is also an important component of a healthy lifestyle. Smoking, alcohol consumption, and drug addiction cause serious harm to human health. In the family, it is essential to develop a strict attitude against such negative behaviors and to explain their harmful effects to children.

Observance of personal hygiene rules is another key factor of a healthy lifestyle. Frequent handwashing, clean clothing, maintaining household cleanliness, and following sanitary requirements help prevent various diseases. Hygiene habits should be developed in children from an early age.

Moral education also plays an important role in establishing a healthy lifestyle in the family. Reading books, fostering respect for national values, and organizing cultural leisure activities contribute to a person's moral development. A spiritually mature individual is more responsible for both their own health and the well-being of others[6].

Establishing a healthy lifestyle in the family is a crucial condition for maintaining health, preventing diseases, and living a happy life. A healthy family is the foundation of a healthy society. Therefore, every family should follow healthy living principles and educate the younger generation in this direction.

Educational institutions are important centers for shaping the intellectual and moral potential of society. Today, educating the younger generation to become physically healthy, mentally strong, and morally mature individuals is one of the priority tasks of state policy. Therefore, organizing and systematically implementing the promotion of a healthy lifestyle in educational institutions is of great importance.

A healthy lifestyle includes maintaining physical health, preventing diseases, increasing physical activity, ensuring proper nutrition, observing personal hygiene, and avoiding harmful habits. By introducing these concepts to students, healthy living skills are formed[9].

In schools, colleges, technical schools, and higher education institutions, the promotion of a healthy lifestyle is carried out in various forms. These include educational hours, sports competitions, health-improving activities, roundtable discussions, seminars, and training sessions. Such activities strengthen students' awareness and responsibility toward their health. In particular, physical education classes and sports activities contribute to the physical development of young people, as well as to the strengthening of their endurance and willpower[8].

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The analysis of mechanisms for forming and developing a healthy lifestyle shows that the population's health status largely depends on their daily lifestyle. Proper nutrition, regular physical activity, avoidance of harmful habits, adherence to personal hygiene rules, and maintenance of mental health are considered the main components of a healthy lifestyle.

The results of the analysis indicate that educational institutions, families, and mass media play an important role in promoting a healthy lifestyle. In particular, regular participation in sports and the formation of a healthy nutrition culture among young people contribute to the improvement of health indicators. In addition, regular preventive medical check-ups increase the possibility of early detection and prevention of diseases[10].

Studies show that individuals who follow a healthy lifestyle have a significantly lower prevalence of cardiovascular diseases, obesity, diabetes, and other chronic illnesses. Furthermore, such individuals demonstrate higher productivity, psychological stability, and overall quality of life.

Based on the results, effective mechanisms for developing a healthy lifestyle include increasing public health literacy, improving sports infrastructure, strengthening awareness campaigns on healthy nutrition, and expanding cooperation between state and public organizations. These measures contribute to strengthening public health and increasing life expectancy[12].

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Promoting a healthy lifestyle also requires the formation of proper nutrition culture. The provision of high-quality and vitamin-rich food in educational institution canteens helps to strengthen students' health. At the same time, it is necessary to conduct awareness-raising activities about the negative effects of consuming carbonated drinks, fast food, and other harmful products[13].

The prevention of harmful habits among young people is one of the key directions of promoting a healthy lifestyle. Smoking, alcohol consumption, and drug abuse cause serious harm to human health. Therefore, it is important to organize preventive activities in educational institutions, hold meetings with specialists, and

strengthen awareness campaigns. Such measures help to develop young people's resistance to harmful influences[11].

Based on the above analysis, it can be concluded that forming and developing a healthy lifestyle is one of the most important factors in strengthening public health. Proper nutrition, regular physical activity, adherence to personal hygiene, avoidance of harmful habits, and maintenance of mental health contribute to improving the quality of life. Moreover, following a healthy lifestyle helps prevent many chronic diseases, increase work productivity, and extend life expectancy[14].

The results of the study show that cooperation between families, educational institutions, the healthcare system, and mass media is essential in promoting a healthy lifestyle. Increasing public health culture and responsibility for a healthy way of life is one of the urgent tasks of today[16].

1. Regular organization of educational events promoting a healthy lifestyle, especially among the population and youth.
2. Wider implementation of special programs on healthy nutrition and physical activity in educational institutions.
3. Increasing the number of sports facilities and mass sports events, as well as expanding access to their use.
4. Regular organization of preventive medical examinations and ensuring active participation of the population.
5. Promoting the benefits of a healthy lifestyle through mass media and internet platforms.
6. Strengthening cooperation between the state, public organizations, and civil society institutions to support projects aimed at raising a healthy generation.

The implementation of these recommendations will contribute to improving public health, strengthening disease prevention, and further developing a culture of healthy living in society[15].

REFERENCES

1. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Protection of Citizens' Health" dated 29.08.1996 No. O'RQ-265-I (with subsequent amendments and additions). <https://lex.uz/docs/26013>
2. Ibragimov A., Karimov Sh. *Fundamentals of a Healthy Lifestyle*. – Tashkent: Fan va texnologiya, 2020.
3. Salimov M. *Human Health and Its Protection*. – Tashkent: O'qituvchi, 2019.
4. Baxriddinov N. S. *Life Safety*. Study guide. – Tashkent: "DIMAL", 2024. – 371 p.
5. Mamadaliyev A. T., Mamadjanov Z. N., Sobirov M. M. *Emergency Situations and Civil Protection*. Textbook. – Tashkent: "DIMAL", 2024. – 416 p.
6. Mamadaliyev Sh. M. *Human Life and Safety*. Textbook. – Namangan: "MUHANDIS NOSIR", 2025. – 451 p.
7. Iskandarova G. T. "Occupational Hygiene" course teaching-methodological complex. – Tashkent, 2017.
8. Karimova L. *Formation of a Healthy Lifestyle in the Family*. – Tashkent: Ma'naviyat, 2022.
9. Yusupov B. *Ecology and Human Health*. – Tashkent: Fan, 2020.
10. World Health Organization (WHO) official website: <https://www.who.int>
11. Mashrapov Q., Yoqubjanova Y., Djurayeva D., & Xasanboyev I. (2022). The role of credit-module system in development of students' specialties in technical higher education institutions. *Theoretical Aspects in the Formation of Pedagogical Sciences*, 1(6), 332–336.
12. Olimjonovich M. Q., & Umarjonovna D. D. (2023). Teaching students in technical specialties based on the conditions of the credit-module system. *Nauchnyy Impuls*, 392.
13. Olimjonovich M. Q. (2025). Assessment of the ecological and economic condition of natural resources and landscapes of Namangan region. *Advances in Science and Environment*, 1(11), 33–35.
14. Mashrapov Q. O., Mo'Minjonov N. N., & Isaboyeva D. S. (2025). *Advantages of Using "Dual" Education in Teaching the Life Safety Science Course*. *Construction and Education*, 4(6), 183–187.

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz HAKIMOV

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Hasan MAQSUDOV

2026. № 6/3

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin. Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

EI.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: @iqtisodiyot_77

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, @iqtisodiyot_77 telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>